

The income statement-a major financial statement of the company

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Abstract: This article provides basic concepts about the income statement, as well as information on definition of its elements and structure and proposals on developing of the statement.

Key words: net sales, cost of goods, gross margin, operating expenses, interest income, income taxes, net income.

The Income Statement gives one important perspective on the health of a business its profitability, but the Statement does not tell the whole picture about a company's financial health. The Income Statement reports on making and selling activities of a business over a period of time: what's sold in the period minus what it cost to make minus selling & general expenses for the period equals income for the period.

The Income Statement documents for a specific period (a month, quarter or year) the second basic equation of accounting: $\text{Sales} - \text{Costs \& Expenses} = \text{Income}$.

Sales are recorded on the Income Statement when the company actually ships products to customers. Customers now have an obligation to pay for the product and the company has the right to collect. When the company ships a product to a customer it also sends an invoice (a bill). The company's right to collect is called an account receivable and is entered on the company's Balance Sheet. Costs are expenditures for raw materials, workers' wages, manufacturing overhead and so forth. Costs are what you spend when you buy (or make) products for inventory. When this inventory is sold, that is, shipped to customers, its total cost is taken out of inventory and entered in the Income Statement as a special type of expense called cost of goods sold. Costs lower cash and increase inventory values on the Balance Sheet. Only when inventory is sold does its value move from the Balance Sheet to the Income Statement as cost of goods sold. When a product is shipped and a sale is booked, the company records the total cost of manufacturing the product as cost of goods sold on the Income Statement.

Gross margin is the amount left over from sales after product manufacturing costs (cost of goods sold) are taken out. Gross margin is sometimes called "gross profit" or the company's "manufacturing margin." Expenses pay for developing and selling products and for running the "general and administrative" aspects of the business. Examples of expenses are paying legal fees; paying a sales person's salary; buying chemicals for the R&D laboratory and so forth. Expenses directly lower income on the Income Statement. Operating expenses are those expenditures (that is, cash out) that a company makes to generate income. Common groupings of operating expense are:

1. Sales & Marketing expense,
2. Research & Development ("R&D") expenses,
3. General & Administrative ("G&A") expenses.

Operating expenses are also called "SG&A" expenses, meaning "sales, general and administrative expense."

If sales exceed costs plus expenses (as reported on the Income Statement), the business has earned income. If costs plus expenses exceed sales, then a loss has occurred. The terms "income" and "profit" and "earnings" all have the same meaning what's left over when you subtract expenses plus

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costs from sales. A manufacturing company's operations are all its actions taken in making and selling products, resulting in both expenses and costs. The term income from operations refers to what is left over after expenses and costs are subtracted from sales.

Paying interest on a loan is a so-called non-operating expense. Likewise, receiving interest on cash balances in the company's bank account is non-operating income. Because it is from non-operating sources, interest income (or expense) is reported on the Income Statement just below the Income from Operations line. Likewise taxes.

Income is the difference between two large numbers: (1) sales and (2) costs plus expenses. More costs plus expenses than sales and the company will show a loss. Less costs plus expenses than sales and the company will show a profit. Remember: Income is not cash. In fact, a very profitable company with lots of net income can also be insolvent, that is with no cash left to pay its bills. Often rapidly growing companies are short of cash even though they are highly profitable. They simply cannot supply out of earnings the capital required for such rapid growth. The words income and revenue are often confused. They mean very different things: "Profit" and "income" do mean the same thing. "Sales" and "revenue" do mean the same thing. Income (also called profits) is at the BOTTOM of the Income Statement. Sales (also called revenue) is at the TOP of the Income Statement.

The Income Statement summarizes and displays the financial impact of: movement of goods to customers (sales) minus efforts to make and sell those goods (costs and expenses) equals any value created in the process (income) All business activities that generate income or result in a loss for a company that is, all transactions that change the value of shareholders' equity are recorded on the Income Statement.

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